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Declaration:

Herewith, I declare that this thesis is the result of my independent work. All sources and auxiliary materials used by me in this thesis are cited completely. The electronic version is identical to the printed version.

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1 Introduction

How did the universe begin?

Where did the universe begin?

What is the humans' position in this vast picture?

These are all big questions, and maybe man's brain is too small to comprehend the extent of the universe. Luckily, there is a part of astrology known as *cosmology* that goes to the bottom of all existence.

Though scientists have researched the topic of cosmology, there is no clear definition. Still, according to NASA [23], it is "the scientific study of the large scale properties of the universe as a whole."

Figure 1: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cosmology>

This may appear as an ordinary picture from a documentary, but in fact, it is a photograph taken by the *Hubble-Telescope* in September 2012, showing the farthest galaxies to be discovered by mankind. Each glimpse of light seems almost irrelevant, but it is really an entire galaxy with hundreds of stars within it.

Albert Einstein. A man everybody knows. But for what?

At the beginning of the 20th century, he was the scientist who changed the view on our universe and created the famous *Relativity Theory* together with the *Einstein Equations*. Suppose you have ever been interested in Einsteins' revolutionary ideas; In that case, the following work will prepare you for its understanding and, at the same time, enlighten your outlook on the *Milk Way*.

To comprehend this thesis, we must lay down the fundamental concepts, and we will start with the *mathematical background*. This is where we repeat the main lectures from differential geometry like manifolds and one-forms. We will also study *Riemannian Geometry* and familiarize ourselves with the terms *connection*, *torsion*, and *curvature*, which will lead us to the formulation of the special theorem: *Levi-Civita connection*. We will finalize the background chapter with *geodesics*.

The main chapter *Cosmology* will be opened with a section about spacetime and the important choice of manifolds. Afterward, we will define the *Cosmological Principle* and the particular *Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker metric*, which is essential for the following sections.

With that being said, the scientists *Edwin Hubble* and *George Lemaitre* formulated a theory, stating that galaxies move away from each other, which will later be discussed as the *Hubble-Lemaitre-Law*.

We will introduce the Hubble constant and take a look at the stars: where are we in comparison to another galaxy and how fast do they move?

Lastly, we will briefly look at the concept of *redshifts* as an add-on to the thesis.

Though it's unclear if there is a boundary ever to be reached by the expansion of our universe, this thesis will argue the legitimacy of the *Cosmological Principle*, the corresponding laws, and theorems that are to be concluded.

2 Mathematical Background

2.1 Manifolds, Charts, and Atlases

In this chapter, we will introduce the standard notion of differential and Riemannian Geometry. For this, we will use the script *Geometry of Black Holes by Professor Anda Degeratu from the summer semester 2020* [2] and Piotr T. Chrusciel's book *Elements of General Relativity* [1]. We will begin with manifolds, charts, and atlases.

Definition 2.1.1 A *topological manifold* M^n of dimension n is a Hausdorff topological space, where each point has a neighborhood homeomorphic to \mathbb{R}^n . This being said, a manifold is locally compact and locally connected, which also implies that a connected topological manifold is path-connected.

Definition 2.1.2 A *chart* on the topological manifold M^n is a pair (U, ϕ) where $U \subset M$ is open and $\phi : U \rightarrow V \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ a homeomorphism onto an open subset $V \subset \mathbb{R}^n$.

The *coordinates* of a point $p \in U$ with respect to ϕ are the coordinates of the point $\phi(p) \in \mathbb{R}^n$.

Definition 2.1.3 An *atlas* of class C^k , respectively C^∞ (or smooth), meaning that this object is k -times differentiable and the k -th derivative is continuous, on M^n is an atlas for which all changes of coordinates are C^k , respectively C^∞ . This means that if (U_1, ϕ_1) and (U_2, ϕ_2) are two non-disjunct charts, then the map:

$$\phi_1 \circ \phi_2^{-1} : \phi_2(U_1 \cap U_2) \rightarrow \phi_1(U_1 \cap U_2)$$

is a diffeomorphism of class C^k , respectively C^∞ . A C^k (or C^∞) **differentiable manifold** is an equivalence class of C^k atlases, respectively C^∞ .

From now on all manifolds are going to be C^∞ -differentiable and we are going to recall some basic concepts in.

2.2 Tangent vectors, spaces and bundles

Definition 2.2.1 A *tangent vector* in $p \in M$ is a map $v : C^\infty(M) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, so that:

1. $v(af + bg) = av(f) + bv(g) \quad \forall f, g \in C^\infty(M) \text{ and } a, b \in \mathbb{R}$
2. $v(fg) = f(p)v(g) + g(p)v(f) \quad \forall f, g \in C^\infty(M)$
3. $v(f) = 0$ for all smooth functions f for which there is a neighborhood U of p in M : $f|_U = 0$

Definition 2.2.2 The *tangent space* $T_p M$ is the set of all tangent vectors at $p \in M$. If (U, ϕ) is a chart with $\phi = (x^1, \dots, x^n)$ as the coordinates, the vectors $\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} \Big|_p$ are defined as:

$$\partial_{i,p}(f) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} \Big|_p(f) := \frac{\partial(f \circ \phi^{-1})}{\partial x^i}(\phi(p))$$

These are the *coordinate tangent vectors* and they build a basis. For efficiency purposes, we will use the following notation:

$$\partial_{i,p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} \Big|_p$$

We will introduce the *tangent bundle*:

Definition 2.2.3 The *tangent bundle* TM is the disjoint union of the tangent spaces $T_p M$ for all $p \in M$:

$$TM = \bigcup_{p \in M} T_p M$$

TM has a canonical differential structure induced from the differential structure on M and exists within twice the dimension of M : $\dim_{\mathbb{R}} = 2n$.

A differentiable **vector field** X is a differentiable section of TM for which we will name the set of these on M : $\mathcal{X}(M)$ or $\Gamma(M, TM) = \Gamma(TM)$.

To clarify this term: say X is a vector field on M and f a smooth function in $p \in M$. Then $X(f) \in C^\infty(M)$ with $X(f)(p) = X_p(f)$.

2.2.1 The Lie-brackets

Definition 2.2.4 *At last, the definition of the **Lie-bracket** of two differentiable vector fields X, Y is:*

$$[X, Y](f) := X(Y(f)) - Y(X(f)) \quad \forall f \in C^\infty(M)$$

Some properties that are frequently going to be used throughout the thesis are:

Lemma 2.2.1 *For $X, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M)$ and $f \in C^\infty(M)$ the following statements are true:*

1. $[X, X] = 0 \quad \forall X \in \mathcal{X}(M)$
2. $[X, Y] = -[Y, X] \quad \forall X, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M)$ (*Anti-symmetry*)
3. $[X, fY] = X(f)Y + f[X, Y] \quad \forall X, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M) \quad f \in C^\infty$

(This Lemma will remain unproven and can be reviewed in differential-geometry.)

We now look at the dual space of $T_p M$.

2.3 One-forms

Definition 2.3.1 *A **one-form** (or **cotangent vector** or **covector**) ω at p is a linear map $\omega : T_p M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ so that:*

$$\omega(av + bz) = a\omega(v) + b\omega(z) \quad \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R} \quad \forall v, z \in T_p M$$

and consequently an element of the dual tangent space $T_p^ M$.*

2.3.1 The Differential

Example 2.3.1 *An example for a one-form is the **differential** of f at p :*

Every smooth function $f \in C^\infty$ defines a one-form $df_p \in T_p^ M$ through*

$$df_p := v(f) \quad \forall v \in T_p M$$

For (U, ϕ) a chart with $\phi = (x^1, \dots, x^n)$ the set of differentials $\{dx^1, \dots, dx^n\}$ form a basis of one-forms dual to the basis $\{\partial_1, \dots, \partial_n\}$ at each point p in U , due to:

$$dx^i(\partial_j) = \delta_j^i \quad .$$

In this basis, the differential df has the decomposition when using the *Einstein Summation* ($a = \sum_{i=1}^n b_i x^i$ is simplified as $a = b_i x^i$):

$$df = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}(f) dx^i$$

Analogue to the tangential bundle, the **cotangential bundle** is defined as:

$$T^*M = \bigcup_p T_p^*M$$

and the set of differentiable one-forms on M will be notated as $\Omega^1(M) = \Gamma(T^*M)$

In the following, we will use the concept of tensors many times, making it important to introduce.

2.4 Tensors

2.4.1 The tensor on a real vector space

Definition 2.4.1 A (s,r) -*tensor* on a real vector space V is multilinear mapping T :

$$T : \underbrace{V^* \times \dots \times V^*}_s \times \underbrace{V \times \dots \times V}_r \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

where V^* is the dual space to V ($V^* := \{ f: V \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \mid f \text{ linear} \}$).

Example 2.4.1 a) A function $v \in V^*$ $w : V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a $(0,1)$ -tensor.

b) The scalar-product λ can also be taken as a $(0,2)$ -tensor since,

$$\lambda : V \times V \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

Similarly defined is the tensor on a manifold:

Definition 2.4.2 For $p \in M$ and

$(\eta^1, \dots, \eta^r, Y_1, \dots, Y_s) \in T_p^*M \times \dots \times T_p^*M \times T_pM \times \dots \times T_pM$ a (r,s) -*tensor* is a \mathbb{R} -linear function:

$$T : \underbrace{T_p^*M \times \dots \times T_p^*M}_r \times \underbrace{T_pM \times \dots \times T_pM}_s \longrightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

$$(\eta^1, \dots, \eta^r, Y_1, \dots, Y_s) \rightarrow T(\eta^1, \dots, \eta^r, Y_1, \dots, Y_s)$$

The space of all these tensors is called the **tensor product** and is denoted by:

$$T_s^r(M) = \underbrace{T_pM \otimes \dots \otimes T_pM}_{r \text{ times}} \otimes \underbrace{T_p^*M \otimes \dots \otimes T_p^*M}_{s \text{ times}}$$

Simplified said, this definition allows two tensors of the same type to be added up and a tensor can be multiplied by a real number. Either way, you receive another tensor of the same type. Say ϕ and θ are covectors. Then one can define (for $X, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M)$) a bilinear map by:

$$\phi \otimes \theta(X, Y) = \phi(X)\theta(Y)$$

Using this notation, we can rewrite the bilinear map g on vectors as following:

$$g(X, Y) = g(X^i \partial_i, Y^j \partial_j) = \underbrace{g(\partial_i, \partial_j)}_{g_{ij}} \underbrace{X^i}_{dx^i(X)} \underbrace{Y^j}_{dx^j(Y)} = (g_{ij} dx^i \otimes dx^j)(X, Y)$$

$(dx^i \otimes dx^j)(X, Y)$

Meaning that from now on we will write:

$$dx^i dx^j := \frac{1}{2}(dx^i \otimes dx^j + dx^j \otimes dx^i)$$

so we can write g in a compact way:

$$g(X, Y) = (g_{ij} dx^i dx^j)(X, Y) \iff g = g_{ij} dx^i dx^j$$

Definition 2.4.3 Say $X, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M)$. A $(0,2)$ -tensor g is called **nondegenerate** if:

$$g(X, Y) = 0 \quad \forall Y \in \mathcal{X}(M) \implies X = 0$$

Now we are prepared to introduce the special *metric tensor*.

2.4.2 The Metric Tensor

Definition 2.4.4 A *metric tensor* g on a smooth manifold M is a symmetric nondegenerate $(0,2)$ -tensor field on M of constant signature.

To clarify this term, it means that g is a $C^\infty(M)$ -bilinear map:

$$g: \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \rightarrow C^\infty(M)$$

Symmetry hereby means that $g(X, Y) = g(Y, X) \forall X, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M)$. Using this definition we get a bilinear map at each point $p \in M$:

$$g_p: T_p M \times T_p M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

This means that if there exists a $v \in T_p M$ then $g_p(v, w) = 0$ for all $w \in T_p M$. Consequently, the map g_p is to be identified with a scalar product. The constant signature means that the signature of g_p as a bilinear form is the same for all $p \in M$. (Notation: $g(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}|_p, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}|_p) := g_{ij}$ which can be represented as a matrix)

In local coordinates we usually write the metric as:

$$g = g_{ij} dx^i dx^j$$

For the next definition let s be the signature of g .

2.4.3 Examples for metrics

Definition 2.4.5 A manifold with a metric of signature s is called a **semi-Riemannian manifold** (or **pseudo-Riemannian manifold**). A metric of signature $s = n$ is called **positive definite** and positive definite metrics are named **Riemannian metrics**.

Its property is that if $g(v, v) = 0$ for all $v \in T_p M$ then $v = 0$.

If the signature is $s = n-2$ then we call this metric the **Lorentz-metric**. An example hereof is the **Minkowski-metric** which is given by the scalar product:

$$\eta(v, w) = \langle v, w \rangle_M = \sum_{i=1}^n v^i w^i - v^n w^n.$$

A popular example for the Riemannian metrics is the **Euclidean metric** on \mathbb{R}^n , defined by the euclidean scalar-product $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_E$ and $v^i \in \mathbb{R}^n$:

$$\langle v, w \rangle_E = \sum_{i=1}^n v^i w^i$$

One more definition as part of this background chapter is:

Definition 2.4.6 Let $\Phi: (M, g) \rightarrow (N, f)$ be a diffeomorphism between two Riemannian manifolds. Φ is called **isometry** when:

$$\forall p \in M \quad \forall v, w \in T_p M : \quad f_{\Phi_p}(d\Phi_p(v), d\Phi_p(w)) = g_p(v, w)$$

The group of isometries of (M, g) will be noted as $Iso(M, g)$.

Lemma 2.4.1 The group of isometries is a Lie-group. Additionally, the dimension of the group of isometries of an n -dimensional pseudo-Riemannian manifold (M, g) is less than or equal to $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$.

(The proof for this lemma can be found on page 206 of Piotr T Chrusciels *Elements of General Relativity*) [1].

Definition 2.4.7 A manifold (M, g) is called *maximally symmetric* if the dimension of $Iso(M, g)$ equals the maximum allowed value: $\frac{n(n+1)}{2}$ in dimension n .

The next problem we'll be going over will be the question of how to move functions or tensors between two manifolds. For this, mathematicians came up with an intuitive solution:

If a map $\phi: M \rightarrow N$ is moving an object from M to N , we will name it *push-forward* while if moving an object from N to M we will call it *pull-back*.

2.5 Pullback and Pushforward

Definition 2.5.1 Let M and N be two smooth manifolds, $U \subset M$ and $V \subset N$ open sets together with a smooth map $\Phi: U \rightarrow V$. For f a function defined on V , it's **pull-back** under Φ :

$$\Phi^* f := f \circ \Phi : U \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$$

If Φ is a diffeomorphism then we can also define the **push-forward** of a function and vector field. The **push-forward of a vector field** X on U is defined as follows:

$$(\Phi_* X)(f) := X(\Phi^* f)$$

and the **push-forward of a function** f is:

$$\Phi_* f := f \circ \Phi^{-1} = (\Phi^{-1})^* f$$

(Note that this is a well-defined function if and only if Φ is a diffeomorphism.)
The **pull-back**, on the other hand, is built as

$$(\Phi^* X)(f) := X(\Phi_* f)$$

Another generalization is the **pull-back of a (p,q) -tensor T** :

$$(\Phi_* T)(w_{(1)}, \dots, w_{(p)} : v_{(1)}, \dots, v_{(q)}) := T(\Phi^* w_{(1)}, \dots, \Phi^* w_{(p)} : \Phi^* v_{(1)}, \dots, \Phi^* v_{(q)})$$

There is one more term to introduce: the *Lie-derivative of a tensor*.

2.6 The Lie-derivative of a tensor field

Definition 2.6.1 *Let $X \in \mathcal{X}(M)$. The Lie-derivative of a (r,s) -tensor field T in direction X is a map:*

$$L_X : T_s^r(M) \rightarrow T_s^r(M)$$
$$L_X(T) := \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Phi_t^*(T) - T}{t}$$

where $\Phi_t : M \rightarrow M$ are diffeomorphisms.

The following definitions are essential to understand for the next chapter: the connection, torsion, and curvature.

2.7 The Connection

Definition 2.7.1 Let M be a C^∞ -manifold. The **connection** ∇ is defined as a map on the following product of vector-spaces:

$$\nabla : \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \longrightarrow \mathcal{X}(M), \quad (X, Y) \rightarrow \nabla_X Y$$

with the following properties:

1. $C^\infty(M)$ - **linear** in X . This means:

$$\nabla_{f_1 X_1 + f_2 X_2} Y = f_1 \nabla_{X_1} Y + f_2 \nabla_{X_2} Y, \quad \forall f_1, f_2 \in C^\infty(M), \quad X_1, X_2 \in \mathcal{V}(M)$$

2. ∇ is \mathbb{R} - **linear** in Y . This means:

$$\nabla_X (aY_1 + bY_2) = a\nabla_X Y_1 + b\nabla_X Y_2 \quad \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R}, \quad Y_1, Y_2 \in \mathcal{V}(M)$$

3. **Leibniz Rule:**

$$\nabla_X (fY) = X(f)Y + f\nabla_X Y \quad \forall f \in C^\infty(M), \quad Y \in \mathcal{V}(M)$$

Depending on the literature, the connection can also be called the **covariant derivative** of Y along X at point p .

2.8 The Torsion of a connection

Definition 2.8.1 The **torsion of the connection** ∇ is defined as:

$$T : \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \longrightarrow \mathcal{X}(M), \quad T(X, Y) := \nabla_X Y - \nabla_Y X - [X, Y]$$

where $[\cdot, \cdot]$ is the Lie-bracket.

Some properties of the torsion are the following:

Lemma 2.8.1 1. *The Torsion is meeting the requirement of linearity in both arguments: \iff*

$$T(f_1X_1+f_2X_2, Y) = f_1T(X_1, Y)+f_2T(X_2, Y) \quad \forall f_1, f_2 \in C^\infty(M), \quad X_1, X_2, Y \in \mathcal{X}(M)$$

(analogue for the second argument)

In other words T is a (1,2)-tensor.

2. *This tensor also fullfills the property of anti-symmetry in X and Y :*

$$T(X, Y) = -T(Y, X)$$

Proof 2.8.1 1. ***Proof of Linearity in the first argument:***

(proof for the second argument is analogue) We want to show:

$$T(f_1X_1 + f_2X_2, Y) = f_1T(X_1, Y) + f_2T(X_2, Y)$$

This can be rewritten, by definition, into:

$$T(f_1X_1 + f_2X_2, Y) = \nabla_{f_1X_1+f_2X_2}Y - \nabla_Y f_1X_1 + f_2X_2 - [f_1X_1 + f_2X_2, Y]$$

$$= f_1(\nabla_{X_1}Y - \nabla_Y X_1 - [X_1, Y]) + f_2(\nabla_{X_2}Y - \nabla_Y X_2 - [X_2, Y])$$

By using the property of linearity of the connection we get:

$$\nabla_{f_1X_1}Y + \nabla_{f_2X_2}Y - \nabla_Y(f_1X_1) - \nabla_Y(f_2X_2) - [f_1X_1 + f_2X_2, Y]$$

$$= f_1\nabla_{X_1}Y - f_1\nabla_Y X_1 - f_1[X_1, Y] + f_2\nabla_{X_2}Y - f_2\nabla_Y X_2 - f_2[X_2, Y]$$

After applying the Leibniz rule we obtain:

$$Y(f_1)X_1 + Y(f_2)X_2 + [f_1X_1 + f_2X_2, Y] = f_1[X_1, Y] + f_2[X_2, Y]$$

Now we can use another Lie-bracket property, which leaves us with:

$$Y(f_1)X_1 + Y(f_2)X_2 + [f_1X_1, Y] + [f_2X_2, Y] = f_1[X_1, Y] + f_2[X_2, Y]$$

Therefore:

$$\begin{aligned} & Y(f_1)X_1 + Y(f_2)X_2 + f_1[X_1, Y] - Y(f_1)X_1 + f_2[X_2, Y] - Y(f_2)X_2 \\ &= f_1[X_1, Y] + f_2[X_2, Y] \end{aligned}$$

which is true.

2. Proof of anti-symmetry:

$$T(X, Y) = \nabla_X Y - \nabla_Y X - [X, Y] = -(\nabla_Y X - \nabla_X Y - [Y, X]) = -T(Y, X)$$

$$\iff -[X, Y] = [Y, X]$$

which is a correct statement due to the Lie-bracket properties. \square

In order to write the torsion in terms of local coordinates we need to introduce the *Christoffel-Symbols*.

2.8.1 Christoffel-Symbols

Definition 2.8.2 The *Christoffel-Symbols* are defined as:

$$\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} := dx^{\mu}(\nabla_{\partial_{\beta}}\partial_{\alpha})$$

which is the abbreviation for:

$$\Gamma_{\alpha\beta}^{\mu} = dx^{\mu}(\nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\beta}}}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\alpha}}) \iff \nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\mu}}}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\nu}} = \Gamma_{\nu\mu}^{\sigma}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^{\sigma}}$$

For $\{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^1}|_p, \dots, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^n}|_p\}$ we now can rewrite the torsion tensor as:

$$T\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\right) =: T_{ij} = \nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^j} - \nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}}\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i} - \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\right]$$

From differential geometry we know the following relationship:

$$\left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\right] = 0$$

which leaves us with:

$$T\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\right) = T_{ij} = \nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j} - \nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}$$

It is important to realize that $\nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}$ can also be understood as:

$$\nabla_{\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}} \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j} = \sum_{k=1}^n \Gamma_{ij}^k \frac{\partial}{\partial x^k}$$

with $\Gamma_{ij}^k \in C^\infty(M)$ (the *Christoffel Symbol*).

With respect to local coordinates (x^1, \dots, x^n) the torsions coefficients are:

$$T_{jk}^i = \Gamma_{kj}^i - \Gamma_{jk}^i$$

2.9 The Curvature of a connection

Definition 2.9.1 *The curvature of the connection ∇ is defined as:*

$$R : \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \longrightarrow \mathcal{X}(M)$$

$$(X, Y, Z) \rightarrow R(X, Y)Z := \nabla_X \nabla_Y Z - \nabla_Y \nabla_X Z - \nabla_{[X, Y]} Z$$

This is a $(1,3)$ -tensor.

Similar to the torsion of the connection, we can paraphrase the definition in terms of local coordinates:

$$R\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x^i}, \frac{\partial}{\partial x^j}\right)\frac{\partial}{\partial x^k} = \sum_{ijk}^l R_{ijk}^l \frac{\partial}{\partial x^l}$$

with $R_{ijk}^l \in C^\infty(M)$.

Lemma 2.9.1 *The curvature of ∇ fulfills \mathbb{R} -linearity in X and Y and is also $C^\infty(M)$ -linear. It also adapts anti-symmetry in X and Y :*

$$R(X, Y)Z = -R(Y, X)Z$$

A further property of the curvature, is the Bianchi-Identity:

$$R(X, Y)Z + R(Y, Z)X + R(Z, X)Y = 0$$

Proof 2.9.1 *1. Proof of anti-symmetry in X and Y :*

We want to show :

$$R(X, Y)Z = -R(Y, X)Z$$

$$\iff R(X, Y)Z = \nabla_X \nabla_Y Z - \nabla_Y \nabla_X Z - \nabla_{[X, Y]} Z$$

$$= -(\nabla_Y \nabla_X Z - \nabla_X \nabla_Y Z - \nabla_{[Y, X]} Z) = -R(Y, X)Z$$

$$\iff \nabla_{[X, Y]} Z = -\nabla_{[Y, X]} Z$$

For a function $f \in C^\infty$ we can use the definition of the Lie-brackets and the linearity of the connection to finish the proof:

$$\begin{aligned} \iff \nabla_{X(Y(f))-Y(X(f))}Z &= -(\nabla_{Y(X(f))-X(Y(f))}Z) \\ \iff \nabla_{X(Y(f))}Z - \nabla_{Y(X(f))}Z &= -\nabla_{Y(X(f))}Z + \nabla_{X(Y(f))}Z \end{aligned}$$

The proofs for the linearity properties, just as the Bianchi-Identity consists of a straightforward use of the curvature definition.

(The proof length exceeds this thesis and is therefore not provided.) \square

A very special connection on a semi-Riemannian manifold is the *Levi-Civita connection*.

2.9.1 The Levi-Civita connection

Theorem 2.9.1 *Let (M, g) be a semi-Riemannian manifold. Then there exists a unique, torsion-free connection ∇ on M , which is compatible with the metric tensor:*

1. $\nabla g = 0$ (the connection is compatible with the metric)
2. The connection ∇ is torsion-free. ($T = 0$)

*This connection is called the **Levi-Civita-Connection**.*

Proof 2.9.2 *Let us start by proving uniqueness. For that, we assume that we already have a torsion-free and a metric-compatible connection ∇ , as given in the theorem. By using the Leibniz Rule we obtain:*

$$\forall X, Y, Z \in \mathcal{V}: \quad 0 = (\nabla_X g)(Y, Z) = X(g(Y, Z)) - g(\nabla_X Y, Z) - g(Y, \nabla_X Z)$$

This can be rewritten to:

$$X(g(Y, Z)) = g(\nabla_X Y, Z) + g(Y, \nabla_X Z)$$

By using cyclic permutations we get:

$$g(\nabla_Y Z, X) + g(Z, \nabla_Y X) = Y(g(Z, X))$$

By using the same permutation one last time with a minus sign we receive :

$$-g(\nabla_Z X, Y) - g(X, \nabla_Z Y) = -Z(g(X, Y))$$

Now we know, that the torsion tensor T of the connection vanishes, meaning that if we sum up the left sides of the equations above, we receive:

$$g(\nabla_X Y, Z) + g(Y, \nabla_X Z) + g(\nabla_Y Z, X) + g(Z, \nabla_Y X) - g(\nabla_Z X, Y) - g(X, \nabla_Z Y)$$

$$= g(\nabla_X Y + \nabla_Y X, Z) + g(Y, \nabla_X Z - \nabla_Z X) + g(X, \nabla_Y Z - \nabla_Z Y)$$

$$= g(2\nabla_X Y - [X, Y], Z) + g(Y, [X, Z]) + g(X, [Y, Z])$$

$$= 2g(\nabla_X Y, Z) - g([X, Y], Z) + g(Y, [X, Z]) + g(X, [Y, Z])$$

\iff

$$\begin{aligned} 2g(\nabla_X Y, Z) &= g([X, Y], Z) - g(Y, [X, Z]) - g(X, [Y, Z]) \\ &\quad + X(g(Y, Z)) + Y(g(Z, X)) - Z(g(X, Y)) \end{aligned}$$

(This equation is known as Koszul's formula.)

Since Z is chosen arbitrary and g is nondegenerate, the uniqueness of the given connection ∇ can be deducted. Leftover to prove is the existence of the Levi-Civita Connection.

For that we define $S(X, Y)Z$ as following:

$$S(X, Y)Z = \frac{1}{2} \left(g([X, Y], Z) - g(Y, [X, Z]) - g(X, [Y, Z]) \right. \\ \left. + X(g(Y, Z)) + Y(g(Z, X)) - Z(g(X, Y)) \right)$$

This term still fulfills linearity with respect to addition and multiplication

$$S(X, Y) f \cdot Z = \\ \frac{f}{2} \left(X(g(Y, Z)) + Y(g(Z, X)) - Z(g(X, Y)) + g(Z, [X, Y]) - g(Y, [X, Z]) - g(X, [Y, Z]) \right) + \\ \frac{1}{2} \left(X(f)g(Y, Z) + Y(f)g(Z, X) - g(Y, X(f)Z) - g(X, Y(f)Z) \right) \\ = f \cdot S(X, Y) Z \quad \forall f \in C^\infty$$

Therefore S is a $(0,3)$ -tensor. Since g is nondegenerate, we can tell that there is a unique vector field $W(X, Y)$ so that:

$$S(X, Y)Z = g(W(X, Y), Z)$$

By executing similar manipulations to the proof of uniqueness we see that:

$$\nabla_X Y = W(X, Y)$$

satisfies the two given properties, and the proof is complete. \square

For the Levi-Civita-connection, the curvature has additional properties:

2.9.2 The Riemannian Curvature Tensor

Definition 2.9.2 *By using the metric, we can change the $(1,3)$ -curvature-tensor into a $(0,4)$ -tensor:*

$$R : \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \times \mathcal{X}(M) \longrightarrow C^\infty(M)$$

which is defined as

$$R(X, Y, Z, W) := g(X, R(Z, U)Y)$$

*We call this tensor the **Riemannian curvature tensor**.*

Corollary 2.9.1 *The Riemannian curvature tensor fulfills the four following symmetries for all $X, Y, Z, U \in \mathcal{X}(M)$:*

1. $R(X, Y, Z, U) = -R(Y, X, Z, U)$
2. $R(X, Y, Z, U) = -R(X, Y, U, Z)$
3. $R(X, Y, Z, U) = R(Z, U, X, Y)$
4. $R(X, Y, Z, U) + R(X, Z, U, Y) + R(X, U, Y, Z) = 0$

(The proof length is a straightforward use of the definitions and is therefore not provided.)

To be able to talk about the upcoming topics, also we need to understand the concept of *Geodesics*. For this, we used David Lindemann's script from 2020: *Differential Geometry, Lecture 17: Geodesics and the exponential map* [6]

2.10 Geodesics

Definition 2.10.1 *Say I is an interval. A smooth curve $\gamma: I \rightarrow M$ is called **geodesic** with respect to a given connection ∇ in $TM \rightarrow M$ if $\nabla_{\gamma'}\gamma' = 0$.*

*We call $\nabla_{\gamma'}\gamma' \in \Gamma(TM)$ the **acceleration** of γ with respect to ∇ . (the apostrophe signifies the differentiation)*

In other words, if the acceleration of a curve vanishes, it means that its velocity vector field is parallel to it.

In case the curve is geodesic with respect to a connection compatible with the metric, like for example the Levi-Civita connection. Then it satisfies the following property:

Lemma 2.10.1 *Let $\gamma: I \rightarrow R$ be a geodesic on a semi-Riemannian manifold (M, g) with respect to a metric connection ∇ . Then $g(\gamma', \gamma'): I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is constant.*

Proof 2.10.1

$$\frac{\partial(g(\gamma', \gamma'))}{\partial t} = \nabla_{\gamma'}g(\gamma', \gamma') = (\nabla'_{\gamma}g)(\gamma', \gamma') + 2g(\nabla_{\gamma'}\gamma', \gamma') = 0 \quad \square$$

Using this Lemma we can also conclude that a geodesic curve γ with respect to the Levi-Civita connection on a Riemannian manifold (M, g) has constant speed.

3 Cosmology

As sources for the following work will be used the script *Geometry of Black Holes* by Dr. Anda Degeratu from the summer semester 2020 [2] and Piotr T. Chrusciel's book *Elements of General Relativity* [1].

3.1 Spacetime

To get to the main topic, first, let us talk about *spacetime*:

To develop mathematical structures, one must define the manifold used. In 1905 *Albert Einstein* came up with this great idea of melting together three space dimensions and time in one manifold. In a first attempt, Einsteins' new *Special Relativity Theory* takes place on the Minkowski spacetime (\mathbb{R}^4, η) , where η is the Minkowski metric. This metric is flat (see page 27/28 in [1]), thus its Riemannian curvature tensor vanishes. Against the recent imagination of space, it represents a universe without gravitation.

Definition 3.1.1 Say (x, y, z) are the spatial coordinates and t denotes the time. The Minkowski metric takes the form:

$$\eta = -dt^2 + dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 = -dt \otimes dt + dx \otimes dx + dy \otimes dy + dz \otimes dz$$

For a tangent vector v with coordinates $v = (v^0, v^1, v^2, v^3)$ we consequently have:

$$\eta(v, v) = -(v^0)^2 + (v^1)^2 + (v^2)^2 + (v^3)^2$$

A tangent vector v to the *Minkowski spacetime* is called:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \text{timelike} & \iff \eta(v, v) < 0 \\ \text{null} & \iff \eta(v, v) = 0, \quad v \neq 0 \\ \text{casual} & \iff \eta(v, v) \leq 0, \quad v \neq 0 \\ \text{spacelike} & \iff \text{otherwise} \end{array} \right.$$

To account for gravity, Einstein needed to allow a larger class of spacetimes which are the 4-dimensional Lorentz manifolds (M, g) . Meaning that in a chart (U, ϕ) of M with coordinates $\phi = (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) = (x^\mu)_{\mu=0, \dots, 3}$ the metric has the form:

$$g|_U = \sum_{\mu, \nu}^3 g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu \otimes dx^\nu$$

with $g_{\mu\nu}$ smooth functions on U so that each point $p \in U$ the matrix $(g_{\mu\nu}(p))_{\mu, \nu=0, \dots, 3}$ has Minkowski signature.

Similar to the Minkowski spacetime (M, η) , a tangent vector $v \in T_p M$ in a Lorentz manifold (M, g) is called:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \textit{timelike} & \iff g(v, v) < 0 \\ \textit{null} & \iff g(v, v) = 0, \quad v \neq 0 \\ \textit{casual} & \iff g(v, v) \leq 0, \quad v \neq 0 \\ \textit{spacelike} & \iff \textit{otherwise} \end{array} \right.$$

The Lorentz spacetime (M, g) is not chosen randomly: one needs an energy-momentum tensor of matter and this triple is required to satisfy the Einstein Equations. Also, we want them to be connected and time-oriented (see page 26).

3.2 Time-orientation and time functions

We as the observer experience changes around us with the help of time, which is why we need to include an additional property on our spacetime (M, g) : we require that our universe is *time-oriented*. This will allow us to talk about timelike vectors which are either *future-oriented* or *past-oriented*.

First, we note that at each point $p \in M$, the set of timelike vectors

$$J_p := \{v \in T_p M \mid g_p(v, v) < 0\} \subset T_p M$$

is a cone in $T_p M$ and it has two connected components: if v belongs to one of them, then $-v$ belongs to the other one.

Lemma 3.2.1 *Let (M, g) be a 4-dimensional connected Lorentz manifold and let J be the set of all timelike tangent vectors:*

$$J := \bigcup_{p \in M} J_p := \{v \in TM \mid g(v, v) < 0\}$$

Then J is an open submanifold in TM , and it has either one or two connected components.

Proof 3.2.1 *For the proof, one needs to define a (smooth) function $f: TM \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $f(v) = g(v, v)$. Since J is the preimage of the interval $(-\infty, 0)$ it is open in TM , which implies that it is an open submanifold. Now let us rewrite J as:*

$$J = \bigcup_{p \in M} J_p := \{v \in T_p M \mid g_p(v, v) < 0\}$$

To check if J has two connected components we define the homeomorphism $\psi: J \rightarrow J$ by $\psi(v) = -v$ and say \mathcal{A} is a connected component of J . The image of connected components under a homeomorphism is connected and therefore, $\psi(\mathcal{A})$ is also a connected component.

If we can show that $J = \mathcal{A} \cup \psi(\mathcal{A})$, then we wrote J as a union of two connected components and we are done.

$\mathcal{B} := \mathcal{A} \cup \psi(\mathcal{A})$ is open and closed in J and consequently the complement $\bar{\mathcal{B}}$ too. By projecting \mathcal{A} and $\psi(\mathcal{A})$ onto M with B and, respectively, \bar{B} , we can rewrite M as $M = B \cup \bar{B}$. Both sets are closed, meaning that if we can show that they are disjoint, the proof is complete.

Let us assume there exists a $p \in B \cap \bar{B}$.

Then there is a $v \in \mathcal{B} \cap T_p M \subset J_p$ and a $w \in \bar{\mathcal{B}} \cap T_p M \subset J_p$. As already clarified previous to the lemma, J_p has two connected components which will be called: J_p^\pm . Without loss of generality, consider $v \in J_p^+$. Then J_p^+ is in \mathcal{B} and since \mathcal{B} is invariant under $v \rightarrow -v$, J_p^- is also in \mathcal{B} .

By using the same argument for w , it follows that $J_p \subset \bar{\mathcal{B}} \cap T_p M$. This statement contradicts the fact that \mathcal{B} and $\bar{\mathcal{B}}$ are disjoint. \square

Now we can introduce the concept of *time-orientation*.

Definition 3.2.1 1. A 4-dimensional connected Lorentz manifold (M,g) is said to be **time-orientable** if J has two connected components.

2. Additionally, a time-orientable Lorentz manifold (M,g) is called **time-oriented** if one of the two connected components of J is chosen and called **future**. The remaining component is called the **past**.

Note that time-orientation labels the timelike tangent vectors either as future-oriented or past-oriented, and this can be done continuously on the Lorentzian manifold.

Example 3.2.1 The Minkowski spacetime (\mathbb{R}^n, η) is time-oriented with a timelike vector $v=(v^0, v^1, v^2, v^3)$ being future-oriented if $v^0 > 0$ and past-oriented if $v^0 < 0$.

On the Minkowski spacetime we have a very special function from $\mathbb{R}^4 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ which assigns to each point p with coordinates $(p^0, p^1, p^2, p^3) = (t, x, y, z)$ the value $p^0 = t$. To generalize this idea, we are going to define the following:

Definition 3.2.2 Let (M,g) be a 4-dimensional time-oriented spacetime. A function $f \in C^\infty$ is said to be a **time-function** on (M,g) if the gradient vector ∇f is timelike and past-oriented at each point.

Example 3.2.2 The function $f(p)=t$ on the Minkowski spacetime is a time-function, since the gradient vector field is timelike and past-oriented:

$$\nabla f = \sum_{\mu,v}^3 \eta^{\mu\nu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x^\mu} \frac{\partial f}{\partial x^\nu} = -\partial_t$$

and

$$g(-\partial_t, -\partial_t) = g(\partial_t, \partial_t) = -1$$

3.3 The Cosmological Principle and Congruences

Let us talk about the main topic: *Cosmological Principle and Congruences*.

Scientists all over the world have been trying to assess the myths behind the universe that also include the understanding of its structure and development. By all means, the following hypothesis is not commonly accepted nor proven, even though this statement is used to develop many new theories.

The main source for the following work will be, once again, *Elements of General Relativity* by Piotr T. Chrusciel [1].

Based on observations of the Cosmic Microwave Background, one is led to assume that at very large structure, our universe looks the same in all directions of observations.

This is the *Cosmological Principle* whose mathematical translation is:

Definition 3.3.1 1. A Riemannian manifold (M,g) is called **homogeneous** if for any two points $p,q \in M$ there exists an isometry that maps p to q .

2. A Riemannian manifold (M,g) is called **isotropic** at $p \in M$ if for all unit vectors $v,w \in T_p M$ exists an isometry $\phi: \phi(p) = p$ and $\phi_*(v) = w$, meaning that the isometry group acts transitively on the set of unit vectors at p (the isometry transports the vector v to w).

(These terms are used to formulate the *Cosmological Principle* as: the universe is homogeneous and isotropic)

Lemma 3.3.1 Let (M,g) be a complete 3-dimensional Riemannian manifold so that either:

1. (M,g) is homogenous and isotropic at some point $p \in M$; or
2. (M,g) is isotropic at every point.

Then (M,g) is maximally symmetric. (see Definition 2.4.7)

Proof 3.3.1 Let us assume we are in case 1 and that q is also a point in M . By the requirements, due to homogeneity, there is an isometry so that: $\phi(p)=q$. Say $u,v \in T_q M$ are two unit vectors, then $\phi_*^{-1}u$ and $\phi_*^{-1}v$ are unit vectors at $T_p M$, but

since M is isotropic at p there exists an isometry $\eta: \eta(p)=p$ and $\eta_*\phi_*^{-1}u = \phi_*^{-1}v$. Therefore: $\phi_*\eta_*\phi_*^{-1}u = v$. By using the push-forward property:

$$\phi_*\eta_*\phi_*^{-1} = (\phi \circ \eta \circ \phi^{-1})_*$$

and since $\phi \circ \eta \circ \phi^{-1}$ is an isometry which maps q to q we can conclude that M is isotropic at q .

In the second case every manifold which is isotropic at all points is homogeneous (this statement remains unproven: for a proof, see: Piotr T. Chrusiels Elements of General Relativity)[1].

However, given these terms in both cases (M,g) is homogeneous and isotropic at every point. Say $p \in M$ and say H is the subgroup of the group of isometries of (M,g) , which is also a Lie-group that leaves p invariant. Then H is 3-dimensional (look at page 204 of Piotr T. Chrusiels Elements of General Relativity)[1].

Consequently, the dimension of $\text{Iso}(M,g)$ is larger than or equal to the dimension of $H+3$ (for further explanation, look at page 204 of Piotr T. Chrusiels Elements of General Relativity)[1]), hence 6. Since $6 = \frac{3(3+1)}{2}$ is the maximum dimension allowed by Lemma 2.4.1 for $\text{Iso}(M,g)$ in dimension 3, it follows that (M,g) is maximally symmetric. \square

In contrast to the first definition of this particular concept, from now on, we are going to use the Lorentz manifold to continue the work (instead of a Riemannian manifold). In the literature, one usually uses the following terms to discuss the Cosmological Principle:

Definition 3.3.2 *The Cosmological Principle states:*

The universe is a time-oriented spacetime (M,g) , admitting a time function t , such that on all the level sets of t :

$$S_\tau := \{p \in M \mid t(p) = \tau\}$$

it looks the same at every point and in all directions.

(Remark: Note that we need to assume that the spacetime is time-oriented since only such spacetimes allow for the existence of time functions. This is because

by definition a time-function $t: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ has the property that its gradient ∇t is timelike and past-oriented at each point.)

Unfortunately, we can not assume that a given observer is, in a way, more special than other ones. Therefore we need to strengthen the mathematical formulation of the Cosmological Principle as follows:

Definition 3.3.3 *The **Cosmological Principle** (physical formulation) states: There exists a family of freely falling observers filling the universe for which the universe looks the same in all directions.*

For the mathematical interpretation of this stronger version, we first need to introduce the notion of *congruence*:

Definition 3.3.4 *Let (M, g) be a spacetime. A **congruence** on (M, g) is a family of freely-falling observers filling the spacetime.*

In general, relativity observers (and test particles) are identified with the curves they move along (their world lines), meaning that all physical objects follow casual curves. Consequently they are free-falling observers when moving along timelike geodesics. In this setup, the existence of a congruence on our spacetime (M, g) is equivalent to the existence of a family of timelike geodesics whose images fill in all M .

By assuming that these geodesics have distinct images we can formulate:

Lemma 3.3.2 *Let (M, g) be a spacetime which is time-oriented. The existence of a congruence on it is equivalent to the existence of a global timelike vector field U on M so that:*

$$\nabla_U U = 0 \text{ and } g(U, U) = -1 \text{ at every point.}$$

Proof 3.3.2 *The existence of a congruence provides a family of timelike geodesics filling the spacetime. By parameterizing each geodesic by proper time, one can define $U(\gamma(s)) := \dot{\gamma}(s)$.*

The geodesic condition $\nabla_{\dot{\gamma}(s)} \dot{\gamma}(s) = 0$ implies the first condition, and due to the geodesic being timelike and parameterized by the proper time, it follows that

$$g(\dot{\gamma}(s), \dot{\gamma}(s)) = -1. \quad \square$$

Now we can paraphrase an even stronger version of the Cosmological Principle:

Definition 3.3.5 *The stronger Cosmological Principle (mathematical version) states:*

The universe is a time-oriented spacetime (M,g) admitting a global timelike vector field U so that:

1. $\nabla_U U = 0$ and $g(U,U) = -1$
2. *There exists a group of isometries of (M,g) which at every point in M acts transitively on the set of directions orthogonal to U .*

As already clarified, property 1. is equivalent to the existence of a congruence whereas the second property rephrases the statement that there are no preferred directions orthogonal to U at any point in M . With this knowledge one can try to show that the stronger Cosmological Principle implies the mathematical version of the Cosmological Principle (Definition 3.3.1).

This requires the existence of a time function t for which we will take a look at the following Lemma:

Lemma 3.3.3 *Let (M,g) be a simply-connected spacetime which satisfies the stronger Cosmological Principle with a timelike vector field U . Without loss of generality, we assume that U is past-oriented.*

Then there exists a time-function $t: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\nabla t = U$.

Proof 3.3.3 *We work in local coordinates (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) . In these coordinates the timelike vector field U is $U = u^\alpha \partial_\alpha$. Due to the definition of the stronger Cosmological Principle, we know about the existence of a group of isometries of (M,g) which at every point in M acts transitively on the set of directions orthogonal to U .*

By assumption, M is a simply-connected spacetime and therefore there exists a function t so that:

$$u_\alpha dx^\alpha = dt$$

This shows the existence of a time function. This time function is only defined on the chosen chart. Due to M being simply-connected, on each chart there exists such a time function and they only differ by a constant. \square

Let $S_t := \{p \in M \mid t(p) = \tau\}$ be the level sets of the time function t given by the previous Lemma.

Lemma 3.3.4 *Let (M, g) be a simply-connected spacetime satisfying the strong Cosmological Principle with a timelike vector field U and time-function $t: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with $\nabla t = U$. Assuming that $0 \in \mathbb{R}$ is a regular value for t , then there exists a small interval $(-\epsilon, \epsilon) \subset \mathbb{R}$ so that for all $t \in S_t$ are smooth 3-dimensional manifolds and the metric g takes the form:*

$$g = -dt^2 + h(t)$$

with $h(t)$ the induced Riemannian metric on S_t by g .

In addition, the isometry group of (M, g) preserves the metric $h(t)$ and acts transitively on each tangent space of each level set S_t .

Proof 3.3.4 *(This is a general proof idea where the full extent can be seen on page 216/217 of [1])*

Let $\{x^i\}$ be any set of local coordinates on S_0 . Since 0 is a regular value for t , it follows that S_0 is a smooth 3-dimensional submanifold of M . We extend these coordinates away from S_0 by requiring that the extended coordinates are constant along the integral curves of U :

$$U(x^i) = 0$$

Then for $(t=x^0, x^i)$ are local coordinates on M and the equation above gives

$$u_\alpha = \partial_\alpha t = \delta_\alpha^0 \iff u^\mu \partial_\mu = u^0 \partial_t$$

Now we already know that $g(u, u) = -1$. Applying this, we obtain:

$$-1 = g_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu = -u^\mu u_\mu = -u^0$$

Therefore $u^0 = 1$, meaning that $u^\mu \partial_\mu = \partial_t$. Thus:

$$-1 = g_{\mu\nu} u^\mu u^\nu = g_{00} (u^0)^2 = g_{00}$$

Moreover

$$0 = u^i = g^{iv} u_v = g^{0i}$$

(All equations together thereby imply $g_{0i} = 0$). In these chosen coordinates we consequently end up with:

$$g = -dt^2 + \underbrace{g_{ij}(t, x)dx^i dx^j}_{=:h(t)}$$

Due to the form of the spacetime metric the isometry group of (M, g) preserves the metric $h(t) = g_{ij}(t, x)dx^i dx^j$ and acts transitively on each tangent space of each level set S_τ . (Meaning that these level sets are also maximally symmetric) \square

To get more insight into the structure of the Riemannian metric (later called: $h(t)$) on each of the level sets S_t we first need to introduce a symmetric 2-tensor A on M which in local coordinates (x^0, x^1, x^2, x^3) is given by:

$$A_{\alpha\beta} = \nabla_{(\alpha} u_{\beta)} := dx^\beta(\nabla_{\partial_\alpha}) + dx^\alpha(\nabla_{\partial_\beta})$$

Lemma 3.3.5 *The tensor A is a space-tensor in the local coordinates (t, x^1, x^2, x^3) given in the proof of Lemma 3.3.4, i.e.:*

$$A_{0\beta} = A_{\beta 0} = 0$$

and it is invariant under the group of isometries of $(S_\tau, h(\tau))$ for all $\tau \in (-\epsilon, \epsilon)$.

Proof 3.3.5 *Indeed, we know that $\nabla_{(\alpha} u_{\beta)}$ is a symmetric tensor field, and we know $u^0 = 1$. We want to show:*

$$A_{0\beta} = 0 = A_{\beta 0}$$

which is equivalent to

$$\nabla_{(0} u_{\beta)} = 0 = \nabla_{(\beta} u_{0)}$$

Due to Lemma 3.3.2 we can tell that

$$u^\alpha \nabla_{(\alpha} u_{\beta)} = 0$$

Similarly, using the definition we obtain

$$u^\alpha \nabla_{(\beta} u_{\alpha)} = \frac{1}{2} \nabla_\beta (u^\alpha u_\alpha) = 0 \quad \text{since} \quad u^\alpha u_\alpha = -1$$

Putting both equations together implies:

$$u^\alpha \nabla_{(\alpha} u_{\beta)} = u^\alpha \nabla_{(\beta} u_{\alpha)} = 0$$

Implicitly we get:

$$\nabla_{(0} u_{0)} = 0 = \nabla_{(0} u_{\beta)}$$

and we are done. \square

Lemma 3.3.6 *Let (M, g) be a maximally symmetric Riemannian manifold and say A is the previously defined tensor on M , which is invariant under the action of the connected component of the isometry group of M . Then A is proportional to the metric.*

Proof 3.3.6 *We claim that A must be proportional to the metric. Consider $p \in S_\tau$ and say H_p is the isotropy group of p . Since in the coordinates (t, x^1, x^2, x^3) $A_{0\alpha}$, the only non-zero components of the tensor A are A_{ij} . Now we introduce*

$$A_j^i = g^{ik} A_{kj}$$

and identify the tensor A with a linear map $T_p S_\tau \rightarrow T_p S_\tau$. A and the metric on S_τ are invariant, the eigenspaces of the tensor A are also invariant under H_p .

From the previous Lemma we already know, that the isometry group acts transitively on unit vectors of $T_p S_\tau$, meaning that $T_p S_\tau$ and $\{0\}$ are the only subspaces invariant under H_p .

Consequently, all eigenvalues of A coincide and for $p \in S_\tau$ we get:

$$A_j^i = f(\tau, p) \delta_j^i$$

for a function f and the transitivity of the action of the isometry on M implies that f is independent of $p \in M$ and the proof is complete. \square

With these Lemmas we obtain the following structure for the spacetime metric g :

Lemma 3.3.7 *Suppose that the metric included on each level set of t is maximally symmetric and that the time derivative of the metric is invariant under the group of isometries of the metric. Then there is a coordinate system in spacetime in which:*

$$g = -dt^2 + R^2(t) \underbrace{g_{ij}(x)dx^i dx^j}_{=:h}.$$

Proof 3.3.7 *As in Lemma 3.3.4*

$$h(t) = g_{ij}(t, x)dx^i dx^j$$

is time-independent whose sectional curvature is constant $k \in \{0, 1, -1\}$. Using the previous Lemma we can tell that there is a function $c(t)$ so that:

$$\frac{dh(t)}{dt} = c(t)h(t)$$

After integration we receive:

$$h(t) = C(t)h(t_0) \quad \text{for} \quad \dot{C}(t) = c$$

and we are done by setting

$$R(t) = b(t)\sqrt{C(t)} \quad \text{and} \quad h = h(0)$$

where $b(t)$ is determined by the sectional curvature of $h(t)$. \square

In view of the results so far, we can formulate the following theorem:

Theorem 3.3.1 *Let (M, g) be a spacetime which satisfies the Strong Cosmological Principle. Then there exists a timelike function $t: M \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ so that in a neighborhood of the time-value $t=0$ the spacetime has the form:*

1. $M = I \times N$ where I is an open interval containing 0 and N is a 3-dimensional smooth manifold.
2. At any time $t \in I$, $(N, g|_{\{t\} \times N})$ is a maximally symmetric Riemannian manifold. In particular, on $I \times N$ the metric g has the form:

$$g = -dt^2 + R^2(t)h$$

with h a Riemannian metric on N .

3.4 The Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker Cosmologies

Let us consider a spacetime (M, g) which satisfies the Strong Cosmological Principle. With Theorem 3.3.1 we know:

1. $M = I \times N$ where I is an open interval containing 0 and N is a 3-dimensional smooth manifold.
2. At any time $t \in I$, $(N, g|_{\{t\} \times N})$ is a maximally symmetric Riemannian manifold.

According to most literature, there is only one metric that satisfies the cosmological principle (and therefore Theorem 3.3.1) that we will get to know as the *Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker metric* (FLRW). This metric is special because it solves Einsteins equations precisely and builds the foundation of modern cosmology. In other words, this metric meets all criteria we have came up with and therefore has a big impact on our imaginations of spacetime.

Now let us talk about the FLRW metric, for which we will use Anja Teuber's *Friedmann-Robertson-Walker-Metrik und Friedmann-Gleichung* from 2008 [3]:

3.4.1 The Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker metric

Definition 3.4.1 *The Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker metric is defined as:*

$$(ds)^2 = -(dt)^2 + R^2(t) \underbrace{\left(\frac{(dr)^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta)^2 + r^2 \sin^2\theta (d\phi)^2 \right)}_{=:h}$$

(The meaning of every parameter will be explained in the formulas derivation)

(Remark: This metric clearly satisfies the stronger Cosmological principle due to its derivation and consequently meets the conclusions from Theorem 3.3.1)

To derive the formula for this specific metric, we can start off a dimension lower than what is needed:

Let $\mathbb{S}^2 = \{(x_1, x_2, x_3) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \mid x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 = R^2\}$ be the 2-dimensional sphere with radius R .

Using the relationship that every point of the sphere fulfills

$$x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 = R^2$$

we can "eliminate" one dimension as following:

$$x_3^2 = R^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2$$

Then:

$$dx_3 = -\frac{x_1 dx_1 + x_2 dx_2}{\sqrt{R^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2}} \quad \text{since} \quad \frac{dx_3}{dx_1} = -\frac{x_1}{\sqrt{R^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2}} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{dx_3}{dx_2} = -\frac{x_2}{\sqrt{R^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2}}.$$

With this, the Euclidean metric on \mathbb{R}^3 restricted to S^2 is:

$$(d\vec{x})^2|_{S^2} = (dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 + dx_3^2)|_{S^2} = dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 + \frac{(x_1 dx_1 + x_2 dx_2)^2}{R^2 - x_1^2 - x_2^2}.$$

Now let us rewrite this into polar coordinates:

$$x_1 := \tilde{r} \cos(\theta), \quad x_2 := \tilde{r} \sin(\theta) \quad \text{with} \quad \tilde{r} \in \mathbb{R}.$$

By plugging it in and simplifying we get (the simplifying steps are not included):

$$(d\vec{x})^2|_{S^2} = \frac{R^2 (d\tilde{r})^2}{R^2 - \tilde{r}^2} + \tilde{r}^2 (d\theta)^2$$

To simplify this term, one can define $r := \frac{\tilde{r}}{R}$ for $r \in [0, 1]$:

$$(d\vec{x})^2|_{S^2} = R^2 \left(\frac{(dr)^2}{1 - r^2} + r^2 (d\theta)^2 \right)$$

The last equality shows a two-dimensional space we know as the surface of a sphere (see [3]).

By replacing R with iR , where i is the complex number, we reverse the sign of the curvature and it becomes negative so that we end up with a hyperbolic space.

A third possibility is to observe $R \rightarrow \infty$, which would leave us with a flat space. These three possibilities can be seen in the following picture:

Figure 2: <http://www.flatuniversesociety.com/>

Now one can repeat this idea for the 3-dimensional sphere S^3 in \mathbb{R}^4 , where you get another angle ϕ when adding polar coordinates ($x_1 = Rr \sin \theta \cos \phi$, $x_2 = Rr \sin \theta \sin \phi$, $x_3 = Rr \cos \theta$). To simplify the understanding of the curvature, we will introduce the parameter k :

For $k = 1$ we will observe a closed space; for $k = 0$ a flat space; for $k = -1$ an open space

By making analogue computations in S^3 , meaning that we would start with:

$$x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 = R^2$$

Then we "remove" one dimension by calculating the differential and reviewing the Euclidean metric. Afterward, we plug in the polar coordinates (as previously defined) and simplify the term. Then we obtain:

$$(d\vec{x})^2|_{S^3} = R^2 \left(\frac{(dr)^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta)^2 + r^2 \sin^2 \theta (d\phi)^2 \right)$$

Now the only part missing to finalize the *Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker metric*, is to include time:

$$(ds)^2 = -(dt)^2 + R^2(t) \underbrace{\left(\frac{(dr)^2}{1-kr^2} + r^2(d\theta)^2 + r^2 \sin^2\theta (d\phi)^2 \right)}_{=:h}$$

The spatial change is now depending on time ($R(t)$), which functions as a time-dependent scalar. (r, ϕ, θ) also have scalar functions, which means that we can assign coordinates to objects in the given manifold. Now the metric tensor can be identified as:

$$g_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{R^2(t)}{1-kr^2} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & R^2(t)r^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & R^2(t)r^2 \sin^2\theta \end{bmatrix}$$

With this metric being introduced, we can study applications of the FLRW-metric: *The Hubble Law*.

3.4.2 The Hubble-Lemaitre Law

As we have just deduced, we can assign coordinates (r, ϕ, θ) to galaxies. To comprehend this Hubble-Lemaitre Law, we will define that our own galaxy is the co-moving spatial origin ($r=0$) and that another galaxy lies at a radial distance r . Thanks to the assumed cosmological principle (to be more precise: due to the universe being homogeneous), we can choose the coordinates of origin, which does not imply that this place is the center of the universe, since any point can be chosen to have $r=0$.

The radial distance D_r between two objects, in this case, our galaxy and the distant galaxy, at any given time t can be calculated with the previously defined FLRW-metric:

$$(ds)^2 = -(dt)^2 + R^2(t) \left(\frac{(dr)^2}{1 - kr^2} + r^2(d\theta)^2 + r^2 \sin^2\theta (d\phi)^2 \right)$$

Herefore we use M. Dalarsson and N. Dalarsson's second edition *Tensors, Relativity and Cosmology* from 2015 [8] and Anja Teubers *Friedmann-Robertson-Walker-Metrik und Friedmann-Gleichung* [3].

Theorem 3.4.1 *The radial distance D_r can be computed with:*

$$D_r = \begin{cases} R(t) \cdot \arcsin(r), & k = 1 \\ R(t) \cdot r, & k = 0 \\ R(t) \cdot \operatorname{arcsinh}(r), & k = -1 \end{cases}$$

Proof 3.4.1 *The information of a cosmological event can travel with a maximum velocity of the speed of light. Meaning that the observer can only notice the event after it already happened. Let us consider an observer at (r_0, ϕ_0, θ_0) . Due to spacetime being assumed to be homogeneous, we can choose $r_0 = 0$ as a convenience and according to the isotropy of spacetime, we can also choose the direction $(\phi_0, \theta_0) = (0, 0)$.*

If we, as the observer, want to see the event, the light must travel on a null geodesic

through r_0 (meaning that the light is traveling along with the "shortest distance" possible through our position).

Now we already know that the light is moving along null geodesics, θ and ϕ are constant, which implies: $d\theta = d\phi = 0$. For the light propagation we require: $(ds)^2 = 0$ and using the FLRW-metric, we receive:

$$(ds)^2 = (d\tilde{t})^2 - R^2(\tilde{t}) \frac{(dr)^2}{1 - kr^2} \stackrel{!}{=} 0$$

After rewriting this into

$$\frac{(d\tilde{t})^2}{R^2(\tilde{t})} = \frac{(dr)^2}{1 - kr^2}$$

and taking the root

$$\frac{d\tilde{t}}{R(\tilde{t})} = \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - kr^2}}$$

we can integrate over the time interval $[0, t]$ and the distance traveled by light $[0, r]$:

$$\int_0^t \frac{d\tilde{t}}{R(\tilde{t})} = \int_0^r \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - kr^2}}$$

$$\Rightarrow D_r = R(t) \int_0^r \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1 - kr^2}}$$

After applying the integral, we can specify D_r as:

$$D_r := \begin{cases} R(t) \cdot \arcsin(r), & k = 1 \\ R(t) \cdot r, & k = 0 \\ R(t) \cdot \operatorname{arcsinh}(r), & k = -1 \end{cases}$$

where r is a dimensionless radial coordinate. \square

Lemma 3.4.1 *Since the radial distance D_r is proportional to $R(t)$, which changes in time, the velocity can be determined by differentiating the distance D_r with respect to time t (here we will use dots as notation of the time differentiation):*

$$v_r = \dot{D}_r = \dot{R}(t) \int_0^r \frac{dr}{\sqrt{1-kr^2}} = \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)} D_r$$

Now all work necessary is done to introduce the *Hubble constant*:

3.4.3 The Hubble Constant

Definition 3.4.2 *The **Hubble constant** is defined as:*

$$H(t) := \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)}$$

and for $t = t_0$ (current time) the Hubble-Lemaitre law states:

$$v_r = \frac{\dot{R}(t_0)}{R(t_0)} D_r$$

where $H(t_0) := H_0 = 67.8 \pm 0.9 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ M parsec}^{-1}$

(This value is obtained from the observations of a Supernovae. The unit "mega-parsec" or mpc is a million parsecs and there are 3.3lightyears per parsec.)

It might be irretating that we talk about the Hubble *constant* when, in fact, it is depending on time. This vlaue also shows that the physical distance between two galaxies changes in time.

However, By using the Hubble-Lemaitre law and the assumption that $R(t)$ is linear: $R(t)=t$ we receive:

$$H(t) = \frac{\dot{R}(t)}{R(t)} = \frac{1}{t}.$$

This lets us calculate the age T of the universe (that is measured from the *Big Bang* until today):

$$T = \frac{1}{H_0} \approx 4.5 \cdot 10^{17} s$$

which is approximately $14 \cdot 10^9$ years.

Figure 3: <https://www.universetoday.com/40064/hubbles-law/>

This Hubble diagram of galaxies shows the relation between velocity and distance, measured in parsecs, among galaxies. The black line represents the expected relation for the chosen cosmology (which in this case is flat). Special herby is the fact, that this is evidence of acceleration of each galaxy apart from the black line, since there are deviations from a linear graph.

Mathematically said:

$$\dot{H} = \frac{\dot{R}^2}{R^2} \left(\frac{\ddot{R}R}{\dot{R}^2} - 1 \right) =: -H^2(q + 1)$$

where for $q := -\frac{\ddot{R}R}{\dot{R}^2} > 0$ the universe is decelerating and for $q < 0$ accelerating. Based on observations, today's value q_0 is

$$q_0 = -0.0639 \pm 0.009$$

which is negative. Meaning that the universe is experiencing an *accelerated expansion*.

3.4.4 The cosmological Redshift

Using the Hubble-Lemaitre law to determine the distance to another galaxy, relative to our galaxy is not the only possible way to do so. In fact, there is a modern and precise way to calculate the distance to another galaxy which can be done by measuring the galaxies Redshift. The content of this chapter is learned from [11].

Figure 4: <https://www.exploratorium.edu/origins/hubble/tools/doppler.html>

Assume the arrowhead represents a galaxy moving to the left. Light emitted from the galaxy moving towards us would be squished (since the galaxy is moving in that direction) and therefore the wavelength would be shorter. Analogue, on earth we receive the light from galaxies that are moving away from us and therefore the wavelength is longer. The shift amount consequently depends on the speed of its galaxy.

Definition 3.4.3 The *redshift* z is defined as the relation between the wavelength change and the original wavelength. Say λ_0 is the original wavelength and λ_1 is the measured wavelength. The redshift z is then defined as

$$z := \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_0}{\lambda_0} = \frac{\lambda_1}{\lambda_0} - 1$$

Theorem 3.4.2 Consider two Galaxies G_1 and G_2 . Using the FLRW-metric, the redshift z can be calculated with

$$1 + z = \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_1} = \frac{\delta t_2}{\delta t_1} \approx \frac{R(t_2)}{R(t_1)}$$

where t_1 and t_2 are the times at which the light left one galaxy, respectively the time when it reached another galaxy and where λ_1 , respectively λ_2 , is the wavelength at which the light is sent of, respectively received. $\delta t_i = \frac{\lambda_i}{c}$ (c equals the speed of light) thereby is the time it takes to send, respectively to receive, a wavelength.

Proof 3.4.2 Say G_1 and G_2 are two galaxies and light leaves G_1 at time t_1 with wavelength λ_1 and is received at G_2 at the time t_2 with wavelength λ_2 . If c denotes the speed of light, then it would take a time

$$\delta t_1 = \frac{\lambda_1}{c}$$

to send one wavelength and a time

$$\delta t_2 = \frac{\lambda_2}{c}$$

to receive one wavelength. Since it does not matter which direction of the wave to follow, we can choose $d\theta = d\phi = 0$ (from the FLRW-metric) to be radial for two light rays that are emitted at t_1 and $t_1 + \delta t_1$ and consider $(ds)^2 = 0 \iff$

$$(ds)^2 = -dt^2 + R^2(t) \frac{(dr)^2}{1 - kr^2} = 0$$

which is equivalent to

$$\frac{dt}{R(t)} = \frac{-dr}{\sqrt{1 - kr^2}}$$

After integration over the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ and the distance traveled by light $[0, r_A]$ we get

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{dt}{R(t)} = \int_0^{r_A} \frac{-dr}{\sqrt{1 - kr^2}}$$

for the first light ray and for the second we receive:

$$\int_{t_1+\delta t_1}^{t_2+\delta t_2} \frac{dt}{R(t)} = \int_0^{r_A} \frac{-dr}{\sqrt{1-kr^2}}$$

As one can see, the right side of both equations are identical since sender and receiver stand still ($r = r_A$ and $r=0$). Therefore we can subtract both equations from one another:

$$0 = \int_{t_1+\delta t_1}^{t_2+\delta t_2} \frac{dt}{R(t)} - \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{dt}{R(t)} = \int_{t_2}^{t_2+\delta t_2} \frac{dt}{R(t)} - \int_{t_1}^{t_1+\delta t_1} \frac{dt}{R(t)} \approx \frac{\delta t_2}{R(t_2)} - \frac{\delta t_1}{R(t_1)}$$

The last equality is not exact, but is fair to assume, since $t_1 + \delta t_1$ is small compared to the rate of change of $R(t)$. Therefore, the last approximation uses:

$$\int_{t_i}^{t_i+\delta t_i} \frac{dt}{R(t)} \approx \frac{\delta t_i}{R(t_i)}$$

Thus, it takes

$$\delta t_2 \approx \frac{R(t_2)}{R(t_1)} \delta t_1$$

to receive one wavelength. In other words, the observer from Galaxy G_2 sees everything slowed down (due to the expansion of the universe) by the factor $\frac{R(t_2)}{R(t_1)}$. Meaning that we see everything "slowed down" and that we can tell how much smaller the universe was when the light left its galaxy and that the wavelength increases with the universe. \square

4 Conclusion

To finalize the thesis, there are still some questions that need to be answered:

4.1 Cosmological Principle and the FLRW-metric

The studies of chapter 3.3 show that a metric that satisfies the Cosmological Principle and therefore Theorem 3.3.1 has the special form:

$$g = g = -dt^2 + R^2(t)h$$

(see page 219 of "Elements of General Relativity" by Piotr T. Chrusciel [1]). With that being said, one can ask himself if the Friedman-Lemaitre-Robertson-Walker metric is the only metric that satisfies the conditions from Theorem 3.3.1.

The answer is no; there is another metric that does not take the special form, given by the theorem but still meets the conditions of the Cosmological Principle. The idea to find another metric satisfying the conditions is to find a time-dependent map. Time-independence is not a requirement nor a conclusion from the Cosmological Principle, meaning other metrics satisfy it. An example for this is

$$g = -dt^2 + \left(\frac{R^2(t)}{1 - kR(t)^2 r^2} dr^2 + r^2 d\omega^2 \right)$$

where $(d\omega)^2 = (d\theta)^2 + \sin^2\theta(d\phi)^2$ (look up FLRW-metric for comparison).

One can see immediately that this metric is not of the form $g = g = -dt^2 + R^2(t)h$ but still satisfies the Cosmological Principle (see page 219 of [1]).

However, there are even more metrics, like for example, the *Kasner metrics* which is a vacuum solution of the Einstein Equations (this metric will not be discussed). So what makes the FLRW-metric special?

The FLRW-metric proposes the simplest form of a non-static (time dependent) universe: a homogeneous, isotropic, and expanding spacetime. It solves Einsteins Equations and, for now, it is the mathematical representaion of everything humanity has observed in the universe. It also takes in consideration time and gravity, which was a big step from the Minkowski spacetime, making the FLRW Cosmologies exceptional.

4.2 Legitimacy of the Cosmological Principle

In this final chapter, we are going to question the Cosmological Principle. Does this assumption make sense in modern physics, and where does its idea originate?

The cosmological principle does not seem to apply to the average human eye when looking around themselves, but on larger scales, like in our universe, it is a concept that makes sense to assume. It is clear that if we take a look at our solar system, it does not look the same. However, if one observes our galaxy, the picture does look very similar in every direction. As one "zooms" out of the galaxy, which can be found in the opening image in Figure 1, no matter where you look, it looks the same (except for local irregularities).

Our *Hubble volume*, which is, roughly said, the space that can be observed for which we can assume that it is isotropic and homogeneous.

Let us say that outside the observable space, our universe is inhomogeneous. Then the required time for the inhomogeneity to spread into our Hubble volume would be about 10 billion years, making the cosmological principle a reasonable assumption.

Even though *Nicolaus Copernicus* is considered to be the father of cosmology [18] for suggesting that earth, together with other planets, are orbiting the sun, *Isaac Newton* is the first one to formulate the Cosmological principle in his book (from 1687): *Philosophiae Naturalis Principia Mathematica* [21]. It was a significant change in mindset since he moved away from the idea of earth being the center of the universe. Instead, he claimed that earth is orbiting around the sun within an in all directions expanding empty space.

This being said, Isaac Newton and Nicolaus Copernicus have built the cornerstone for future discoveries, like Einstein's Special Relativity Theory, and gave reason to study our universe and its secrets as part of this Bachelor Thesis.

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